

Table 3. Grain yield and its contributing characters under waterlogged (0-50 cm depth) conditions.

Germplasm/ cultivar	Plant height (cm)	Days to 90% flowering	Single panicle weight (g)	PBT ^a (no. m ⁻²)	Harvest index (%)	Grain yield (g m ⁻²)
FR13A	158	145	3.63	135	23.1	386
Sabita	184	141	4.46	95	31.0	421
CR380-10	169	149	4.20	138	33.5	472
Matia	178	149	2.58	110	21.6	215
ARC18112	154	98	2.59	118	24.9	260
ARC18101	158	121	3.03	100	31.2	261
ARC18104	152	131	3.75	104	29.4	347
ARC18172	185	110	2.50	109	27.9	212
ARC18198	122	92	2.34	133	38.4	267
Tulasi	145	141	4.23	153	29.4	516
Mean	160	128	3.33	119	29.0	336
CV	11.4	15.8	23.2	15.2	16.3	30.8

^aPBT = panicle-bearing tillers.

(Table 3). For the rainfed lowlands of eastern India, plants with different maturity periods are desirable for different locations. Therefore, plant breeders could employ the genotypes mentioned here. ■

Comments. If you have comments or suggestions about the IRRN, please write to the editor.

Yield potential

Physiological basis of heterosis in rice

A.K. Singh and F.U. Zaman, Division of Genetics, Indian Agricultural Research Institute, New Delhi 110012, India

New plant types and hybrids are physiologically more efficient. They have a higher biomass than inbred varieties and a comparable harvest index. Increasing biomass yield and maintaining a high harvest index are the main breeding strategies for achieving another breakthrough in rice yield. Biomass is a complex trait governed by a number of morphophysiological components. We attempted to analyze the physiological components of biomass and to study the character association and path relationship among its components. A strategy to select parents for developing hybrids and pedigree breeding based on physiological efficiency are outlined.

The material for this study consisted of 15 F₁s and 6 parents from a 6 × 6 half diallel involving diverse parents for physiological efficiency. The experiment was conducted in a randomized block design with three replications. Data were recorded on characters such as biological yield, grain yield, harvest index, days to 50% flowering, grain-filling duration, days to maturity, cumulative growth rate (CGR), relative growth rate (RGR), net assimilation

rate (NAR), leaf area ratio (LAR), leaf area index (LAI), leaf area duration (LAD), and leaf area plant⁻¹ at different growth stages. Correlation, path effects, and heterosis were estimated.

Grain yield, CGR, LAI, LAD, and leaf area at seedling, tillering, flowering, and maturity showed a highly significant positive association with biological yield. The cross, Jaya/Swarnaprabha, which exhibited a high heterobeltiosis for biological yield (54.9%), also showed a significant positive heterosis for grain yield, harvest index, CGR, LAI, and leaf area plant⁻¹. Characters that showed a negative association with biological yield did not exhibit any positive heterosis. It is therefore evident that, to develop heterotic hybrids, we should identify parents with high physiological efficiency in terms of CGR, LAI, LAD, and leaf area plant⁻¹. Because characters such as NAR, LAR, LAD, and leaf area showed a high positive direct path effect, direct selection for these traits should be effective.

With this understanding of the key physiological determinants of biological yield, the interrelationship among these components, and their direct and indirect effects on biological yield, we can make a better selection of parents. This approach should help develop superior hybrids and generate valuable breeding material for pedigree selection. ■

Physiological efficiency of rice hybrids

K.V. Sitaramaiah, J. Madhuri, and N.S. Reddy, Rice Research Unit, Agricultural College Farm, Bapatla 522101, India

Heterosis observed in hybrids is the result of various physiological processes that occur at different stages of plant growth. A precise knowledge of the factors that contribute to heterotic vigor would help to manipulate heterosis expression in hybrids. We made a study to assess the physiological efficiency of rice hybrids during the crop growth period and to analyze the factors that contribute to heterosis expression. Six promising experimental rice hybrids were evaluated along with the popular check varieties Samba Mahsuri and Chaitanya during the 1995 wet season. Crop growth rate (CGR), leaf area index (LAI), and biomass production (BMP) were estimated at 15-d intervals from 15 to 60 d after planting (DAP). Harvest index (HI) and grain yield were recorded at harvest.

CGR increased up to 45 DAP and decreased later in all hybrids and checks. LAI, however, consistently increased from 15 to 60 DAP and hybrids recorded a higher LAI from 30 DAP onward compared with the checks. The high initial CGR was not maintained to the later growth stages

or translated into higher yields. Early vigor was probably sacrificed to ensure a better canopy structure at the late growth stages and better partitioning of photosynthates to grain. This was well exhibited by the hybrids, especially MTUHR2033, MTUHR2020, and MTUHR2037, which had significantly higher grain yields. These hybrids also recorded greater BMP and HI. Though the check varieties and hybrids did not differ for BMP, the hybrids showed a superior performance because of more grains per panicle, which was indicated by a higher HI. Two hybrids, MTUHR2024 and MTUHR2029, however, showed an inferior performance compared with the best check Chaitanya in BMP, HI, and grain yield.

Heterosis is a highly cross-specific phenomenon. To use heterosis successfully to increase grain yield, parental genotypes need to be selected from modern cultivars with a high potential. The physiological efficiency of F_1 hybrids at the vegetative stage is a useful indication of heterosis for grain yield. MTUHR2033 and MTUHR2020, which showed such physiological efficiency, hold good promise. ■

Performance of hybrid rice in south Karnataka

M. Rudraradhya, S. Panchaksharaiah, and B. R. Patil, University of Agricultural Sciences, Shimoga Unit, Bangalore, India

At the agricultural research stations at Honnaville and Kathalagere, we evaluated elite hybrids. We also investigated the fixing of isolation distance, number of seedlings to be planted hill⁻¹, and N management. Among the various hybrids tested in 1991-94, IR58025A / IR9761-19-1R was found to be superior to inbred variety Mangala. This hybrid recorded an average yield of 5.6 and 4.9 t ha⁻¹, respectively, at Honnaville and Kathalagere. Mangala yielded 3.8 and 3.6 t ha⁻¹, respectively, at those two centers. This hybrid also performed well in on-farm trials in the districts of Chikamagalore, Hassan, Mysore, and Shimoga, with a mean grain yield of 5.9 t ha⁻¹ vs 4.7 t ha⁻¹ for Mangala. This hybrid was named Karnataka Rice Hybrid 1 (KRH1) and released for general cultivation in the southern transition zone.

Similarly, another F_1 hybrid, IR58025A / KMR 3, had an average yield of 6.6 t ha⁻¹ vs 5.1 t ha⁻¹ for Jaya. This hybrid was found promising because it matured in 125-130 d, similar to the popular inbred variety. In 12 on-farm trials, this hybrid registered a mean grain yield of 7.3 t ha⁻¹ vs 6.0 t ha⁻¹ for the standard check Jaya. This hybrid was named Karnataka Rice Hybrid 2 and released for general cultivation in 1996. The present recommended dose of 100-50-50 kg NPK ha⁻¹ for the varieties was found to be equally effective for the two hybrids. There was no difference in yield among plots planted with one, two, three, four, or five seedlings hill⁻¹ in both the dry and wet seasons. Tillering ability in the hybrids was found to be very good. Therefore, planting 1 seedling hill⁻¹ ensured an economical seed input cost. In the studies conducted on isolation distance, seed set decreased with every increase in the isolation distance. This called for a revision of isolation distance for each hybrid through investigations at specific locations. ■

Crop and resource management

Physiology and plant nutrition

Effect of salinity on growth, chlorophyll content, and flag leaf area of rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) genotypes

M. Yasin Ashraf and Yousaf Ali, Nuclear Institute for Agriculture and Biology (NIAB), Jhang Road, P.O. Box 128, Faisalabad, Pakistan

Rice is the most important food crop, feeding more than half of the world's population. To feed this ever-growing population, an increase in the cultivation of food crops is essential, which is possible by increasing cultivable lands.

Lands in Pakistan that are available for cultivation suffer from problems of

salinity / sodicity. So we urgently need to select or develop salt-tolerant rice varieties or methods to increase the yield per unit area.

Although yield is the result of interactions in the genetic makeup of genotypes, it has been suggested that by increasing photosynthetic efficiency, crop production could be increased (Ashraf et al 1995). Photosynthetic efficiency depends on leaf area, chlorophyll content, stomatal response, gas exchange, etc. We therefore used a physiological-genetic approach to test whether genotypes sensitive to or tolerant of salt differ in their photosynthetic efficiency.

For this purpose, a gravel culture experiment was conducted in a growth cabinet maintained at 30/25 + 2 °C day / night temperature and a photoperiod of 10 h, to study the effect of salinity created by mixed salt (Na_2SO_4 , CaCl_2 , MgCl_2 , and NaCl in the ratio of 6.33:3.58:1:2.28) and NaCl only on growth and photosynthetic activity of rice genotypes. Thirty-day-old seedlings of five rice genotypes—BH-5-89, BH-3-89, RST-1-86, RST-2-84, and Bas370×NR1—were acquired from the rice section of the Mutation Breeding Division of the NIAB, Faisalabad, Pakistan.